

Supplementary material for “IaC Generation with LLMs: An Error Taxonomy and A Study on Configuration Knowledge Injection”

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1 Supplementary Material Introduction

This supplementary material contains the replication package link and the examples of the taxonomy error category, subcategory, and atomic errors.

2 Replication Package

The replication package of the research is also reported inside the manuscript. For completeness, we provide the link to access the replication package here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20272829> The package includes the enhanced IaC-eval framework code and its related revised dataset. It also contains the complete implementation of the knowledge injection techniques, along with their experiments and the associated results. The scripts for statistical analysis are also provided in the package. More information is available in the paper manuscript.

3 Technical Validation Errors

Table 1. Dimension 1: Technical Validation Errors in LLM-Generated Terraform Code

Error Category	Error Sub-Category	Atomic Error	GPT-4o
Syntax	Terraform language error	Breaks basic syntax rules or structure	4
	Format error	Uses invalid names or formatting	8
Schema	Argument error	Uses an argument that is not allowed	326
		Leaves out a required argument	140
		Assigns a wrong or unsupported value	13
		Uses a reserved word as an argument name	2
		Combines arguments that conflict	3
		Repeats the same argument twice	4
	Attribute error	Refers to an attribute that does not exist	3
		Uses an attribute in the wrong way	5
	Block error	Adds a block type that is not supported	104
		Misses blocks that are required	64
Adds more blocks than allowed		1	
Resource error	Uses a resource type that does not exist	44	
	Refers to a resource that is invalid or missing	10	
	Declares the same resource more than once	12	
Runtime	Environment error	Refers to a file that cannot be found	23
	Provider error	Refers to a provider that is not configured	1
		Configures the same provider multiple times	6
	Version error	Uses an invalid or unsupported version range	1

Table 2. Dimension 2: Technical Validation Errors in LLM-Generated Terraform Code

Error Category	Error Sub-Category	GPT-4o
LLM Generation Failure Type	Factual Incorrectness	503
	Structural Deficit	12
	Contextual Reasoning Failure	54
	Incompleteness	205

3.1 Technical Validation Error Examples

Table 3. Dimension 1: Technical Validation Error Examples - Syntax Error Category

Atomic Error	Dataset Infrastructure-as-Code	Generated Infrastructure-as-Code
Breaks basic syntax rules or structure	<pre># 252 resource "aws_chime_voice_connector" "default" { name = "vc-name-test" require_encryption = true }</pre>	<pre># 252 resource "aws_chime_voice_connector" "example" { name = "example-voice-connector" region = "us-east-1" require_encryption = true logging_configuration { enable_media_metric_logging = true } @depends_on = [aws_iam_role.chime_voice_connector_role] }</pre>
Uses invalid names or formatting	<pre># 184 resource "aws_sagemaker_model" "sagemaker_model" { name = "my-model" execution_role_arn = aws_iam_role.sagemaker_exec_role.arn primary_container { ... } }</pre>	<pre>#184 resource "aws_sagemaker_model" "sagemaker_model" { name = "my_model" execution_role_arn = aws_iam_role.sagemaker_exec_role.arn primary_container { ... } }</pre>

Table 4. Dimension 1: Technical Validation Error Examples - Argument Error Sub-Category

Atomic Error	Dataset Infrastructure-as-Code	Generated Infrastructure-as-Code
Uses an argument that is not allowed	<pre># 191 resource "aws_ec2_fleet" "ec2_fleet" { launch_template_config { launch_template_specification { ... } } target_capacity_specification { ... } excess_capacity_termination_policy = "termination" replace_unhealthy_instances = true terminate_instances = true }</pre>	<pre>#191 resource "aws_ec2_fleet" "my_ec2_fleet" { iam_fleet_role = aws_iam_role.ec2_instance_role.arn target_capacity_specification { ... } launch_template_config { ... } }</pre>
Leaves out a required argument	<pre>#138 resource "aws_elasticache_user_group" "example"{ engine = "REDIS" user_group_id = "userGroupId" user_ids = [aws_elasticache_user.default.user_id] lifecycle { ignore_changes = [user_ids] } }</pre>	<pre>#138 resource "aws_elasticache_user_group" "example_user_group" { user_group_id = "existing-user-group-id" }</pre>

<p>Assigns a wrong or unsupported value</p>	<pre># 325 resource "aws_db_instance" "test" { identifier = "metricbeat-test-\${random_id.suffix.hex}" allocated_storage = 20 // Gigabytes engine = "mysql" instance_class = "db.t2.micro" db_name = "metricbeattest" username = "foo" password = random_password.db.result skip_final_snapshot = true // Required for cleanup }</pre>	<pre>resource "aws_db_instance" "mysql_db" { identifier = random_string.db_identifier.result allocated_storage = 20 engine = "mysql" instance_class = "db.t2.micro" master_username = "admin" master_password = random_string.db_password.result db_name = "mydatabase" skip_final_snapshot = true ... }</pre>
<p>Uses a reserved word as an argument name</p>	<pre># 327 resource "aws_db_subnet_group" "db-subnet-group" { name = "db-subnet-group" subnet_ids = module.vpc.public_subnets }</pre>	<pre># 327 resource "aws_db_subnet_group" "default" { name = "default" subnet_ids = [aws_subnet.public_subnet_1.id, aws_subnet. public_subnet_2.id] tags = { Name = "default" } }</pre>
<p>Combines arguments that conflict</p>	<pre>#397 terraform { ... } provider "aws" { ... } data "aws_availability_zones" "available" { ... } module "vpc" { ... } resource "aws_security_group" "lb-sg" { ... } resource "aws_vpc_security_group_ingress_rule" "lb-sg-ingress-rule" { ... } resource "aws_vpc_security_group_egress_rule" "lb-sg-egress-rule" { ... } resource "aws_lb" "test" { subnets = module.vpc.public_subnets internal = false load_balancer_type = "application" security_groups = [aws_security_group.lb-sg.id] } resource "aws_lb_listener" "my_listener" { ... } resource "aws_lb_target_group" "target_group" { ... } ...</pre>	<pre>#397 provider "aws" { region = "us-east-1" } resource "aws_lb" "main" { name = "main-load-balancer" internal = false load_balancer_type = "application" security_groups = [aws_security_group.lb-sg.id] enable_deletion_protection = false idle_timeout = 60 enable_http2 = true tags = { Name = "Main_Load_Balancer" } } resource "aws_security_group" "lb_sg" { ... } resource "aws_lb_listener" "http" { ... } resource "aws_vpc" "main" { ... }</pre>

Repeats the same argument twice	<pre># 256 resource "aws_chime_voice_connector" "vc2" { name = "connector-test-2" require_encryption = true aws_region = "us-west-2" }</pre>	<pre># 256 resource "aws_chime_voice_connector" "connector2" { name = "VoiceConnector2" region = "us-east-1" require_encryption = true voice_connector_id = "vc-2" require_encryption = true encryption = { encryption_status = "ENABLED" } }</pre>
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Table 5. Dimension 1: Technical Validation Error Examples - Attribute Error Sub-Category

Atomic Error	Dataset Infrastructure-as-Code	Generated Infrastructure-as-Code
Refers to an attribute that does not exist	<pre>#12 resource "aws_route53_record" "blue" { zone_id = aws_route53_zone.main.zone_id name = "app.example.com" type = "CNAME" ttl = "60" weighted_routing_policy { weight = 120 } set_identifier = "BlueEnvironment" records = [aws_elastic_beanstalk_environment.blue.cname] }</pre>	<pre>#12 resource "aws_route53_record" "blue" { zone_id = aws_route53_zone.main.id name = "myapp.example.com" type = "A" alias { name = aws_elastic_beanstalk_environment.blue. endpoint_url zone_id = aws_elastic_beanstalk_environment.blue.cname_suffix evaluate_target_health = true } ttl = 60 }</pre>
Uses an attribute in the wrong way	<pre>#166 resource "aws_dynamodb_table" "example" { name = "example-name" read_capacity = 10 write_capacity = 10 hash_key = "exampleHashKey" attribute { name = "exampleHashKey" type = "S" } }</pre>	<pre>#166 resource "aws_dynamodb_table_item" "example_item" { table_name = aws_dynamodb_table.example.name hash_key = aws_dynamodb_table.example.hash_key item = jsonencode(id = "1" name = "Item 1" quantity = 100) }</pre>

Table 6. Dimension 1: Technical Validation Error Examples - Block Error Sub-Category

Atomic Error	Dataset Infrastructure-as-Code	Generated Infrastructure-as-Code
Adds a block type that is not supported	<pre>#19 resource "aws_elastic_beanstalk_environment" " microservice_env1" { name = "microservice-env1" application = aws_elastic_beanstalk_application. microservice_app.name solution_stack_name = "64bit_Amazon_Linux_2023_v4.3.0_ running_Python_3.9" setting { ... } ... } }</pre>	<pre>#19 resource "aws_elastic_beanstalk_environment" "env1" { name = "my-env-1" application = aws_elastic_beanstalk_application.app1. name solution_stack = "64bit_Amazon_Linux_2_v3.2.0_running_ Apache" setting { ... } tier type = "WebServer" version = "1.0" }</pre>
Misses blocks that are required	<pre>#34 resource "aws_codebuild_project" "example" { name = "Row2CodeBuild" description = "Row2CodeBuild" build_timeout = 5 service_role = aws_iam_role.example.arn artifacts type = "NO_ARTIFACTS" ... }</pre>	<pre>#34 resource "aws_codebuild_project" "example" { name = "example-codebuild-project" description = "Example_AWS_CodeBuild_project" build_timeout = 5 ... service_role = aws_iam_role.codebuild_role.arn }</pre>
Adds more blocks than allowed	<pre>#5 resource "aws_route53_record" "replica_1_cname" { zone_id = aws_route53_zone.main.zone_id name = "replica1.example53.com" type = "CNAME" records = [aws_db_instance.replica_1.endpoint] ttl = "60" weighted_routing_policy { weight = 10 } set_identifier = "replica-1-record" }</pre>	<pre>#5 resource "aws_route53_record" "weighted_record" { zone_id = aws_route53_zone.main.zone_id name = "db" type = "A" ttl = 60 weighted_routing_policy { set_identifier = "replica-1" ... } weighted_routing_policy { set_identifier = "replica-2" ... } }</pre>

Table 7. Dimension 1: Technical Validation Error Examples - Resource Error Sub-Category

Atomic Error	Dataset Infrastructure-as-Code	Generated Infrastructure-as-Code
Uses a resource type that does not exist	<pre>#15 resource "aws_elastic_beanstalk_application" "my_app" { name = "my-app" description = "My_awesome_application" }</pre>	<pre>#15 resource "aws_beanstalk_application" "app" { name = "my-beanstalk-app" }</pre>

<p>Refers to a resource that is invalid or missing</p>	<pre>#91 resource "aws_subnet" "private-us-east-1a" { vpc_id = aws_vpc.main.id cidr_block = "10.0.1.0/24" } resource "aws_eks_cluster" "example" { name = "test" version = "test-version" role_arn = aws_iam_role.example.arn vpc_config { subnet_ids = [aws_subnet.private-us-east-1a.id,] } }</pre>	<pre>#91 resource "aws_eks_cluster" "example" { name = "example" role_arn = aws_iam_role.eks_cluster_role.arn vpc_config { subnet_ids = [aws_subnet.example_subnet.id] } }</pre>
<p>Declares the same resource more than once</p>	<pre>#216 resource "aws_rds_cluster" "default" { cluster_identifier = "aurora-cluster-demo" engine = "aurora-postgresql" availability_zones = ["us-east-1a", "us-east-1b", "us-east-1c"] database_name = "mydb" master_username = "USERNAME" master_password = "PASSWORD" backup_retention_period = 5 preferred_backup_window = "07:00-09:00" skip_final_snapshot = true }</pre>	<pre>#216 resource "aws_rds_cluster" "aurora_postgresql" { cluster_identifier = "aurora-cluster" engine = "aurora-postgresql" master_username = "admin" master_password = "SuperSecretPassword123" ... } resource "aws_rds_cluster" "aurora_postgresql" { db_cluster_parameter_group_name = aws_rds_cluster_parameter_group.aurora_pg.name }</pre>

Table 8. Dimension 1: Technical Validation Error Examples - Runtime Error Category

Atomic Error	Dataset Infrastructure-as-Code	Generated Infrastructure-as-Code
<p>Refers to a file that cannot be found</p>	<pre>#50 resource "aws_lambda_function" "hello_pizza" { function_name = "hello_pizza" role = aws_iam_role.iam_exec_role.arn filename = data.archive_file.hello_pizza.output_path source_code_hash = data.archive_file.hello_pizza.output_base64sha256 handler = "hello_pizza.handler" runtime = "python3.12" }</pre>	<pre>#50 resource "aws_lambda_function" "pizza_ordering_function" { function_name = "PizzaOrderingFunction" role = aws_iam_role.lambda_execution_role.arn handler = "index.handler" runtime = "nodejs14.x" source_code_hash = filebase64sha256("lambda.zip") environment { VAR1 = "value1" } }</pre>

Refers to a provider that is not configured	<pre>#99 terraform { ... } provider "aws" { region = "us-east-1", profile = "admin-1" } resource "aws_vpc" "main" { ... } resource "aws_subnet" "example1" { ... } resource "aws_subnet" "example2" { ... } resource "aws_iam_role" "example1" { ... } resource "aws_iam_role_policy_attachment" " eks_cluster_policy" { ... } resource "aws_iam_role_policy_attachment" " eks_service_policy" { ... } resource "aws_eks_cluster" "example" { ... } data "aws_iam_policy_document" "assume_role" { ... } resource "aws_iam_role" "example" { ... } resource "aws_iam_role_policy_attachment" "example_s3" { ... } resource "aws_eks_pod_identity_association" "example" { ... }</pre>	<pre>#99 provider "aws" { region = "us-west-2" } data "aws_iam_policy_document" "example" { ... } resource "aws_iam_role" "example" { } resource "aws_iam_policy" "s3_read_only" { } resource "aws_iam_role_policy_attachment" " example_s3_read_only" { } resource "kubernetes_namespace" "example" { ... } resource "kubernetes_service_account" "example" { ... } resource "eks_pod_identity_mapping" "example" { cluster_name = "example" service_account = kubernetes_service_account.example.metadata[0].name namespace = kubernetes_namespace.example.metadata[0].name role_arn = aws_iam_role.example.arn }</pre>
Configures the same provider multiple times	<pre>#163 provider "aws" { region = "us-east-1" profile = "admin-1" assume_role { role_arn = "arn:aws:iam::590184057477:role/yicun-iac" } }</pre>	<pre>#163 provider "aws" { region = "us-east-1" } resource "aws_dynamodb_table" "example_table_east" { ... } provider "aws" { region = "us-west-1" }</pre>
Uses an invalid or unsupported version range	<pre>#47 terraform { required_providers { aws = { source = "hashicorp/aws" version = "> 5.75" } } }</pre>	<pre>#47 terraform { required_providers { aws = { source = "hashicorp/aws" version = "> 3.0" } } required_version = ">= 0.12" }</pre>

4 Intent Validation Errors

Table 9. Dimension 1: Intent Validation Errors in LLM-Generated Terraform Code

Error Category	Error Sub-Category	Atomic Error	GPT-4o
Intent	Misaligned resource	Fails to include a necessary resource	14
		Uses a resource that does not match the intent	17
		Uses a resource that is outdated or deprecated	11
	Misconfiguration	Uses correct resources but misconfigured them	4

Table 10. Dimension 2: Intent Validation Errors in LLM-Generated Terraform Code

Error Category	Error Sub-Category	GPT-4o
LLM Generation Failure Type	Factual Incorrectness	11
	Structural Deficit	0
	Contextual Reasoning Failure	21
	Incompleteness	14

4.1 Intent Validation Error Examples

Table 11. Dimension 1: Intent Validation Error Examples - Misaligned Errors Sub-Category

Atomic Error	Dataset Infrastructure-as-Code	Generated Infrastructure-as-Code
Fails to include a necessary resource	<pre>#4 terraform { required_providers { ... } provider "aws" { ... } resource "aws_vpc" "main" ... resource "aws_db_instance" "internal" { ... } resource "aws_db_instance" "public" { ... } resource "aws_db_subnet_group" "main" { ... } data "aws_availability_zones" "available" { ... } resource "aws_subnet" "maina" { ... } resource "aws_subnet" "mainb" { ... } resource "aws_route53_zone" "public" { ... } resource "aws_route53_zone" "private" { ... } resource "aws_route53_record" "public_db" { ... } resource "aws_route53_record" "internal_db" { ... }</pre>	<pre>#4 provider "aws" { region = "us-west-2" } resource "aws_route53_zone" "private" { ... } resource "aws_route53_zone" "public" { ... } resource "aws_db_subnet_group" "main" { ... } resource "aws_db_instance" "internal" { ... } resource "aws_db_instance" "public" { ... } resource "aws_route53_record" "internal_db" { ... } resource "aws_route53_record" "public_db" { ... }</pre>

Uses a resource that does not match the intent	<pre>#29 provider "aws" { region = "us-east-1" } resource "aws_elastic_beanstalk_application" "tftest" { ... } resource "aws_elastic_beanstalk_configuration_template" " tf_template" { ... }</pre>	<pre>#29 provider "aws" { region = "us-east-1" } resource "aws_iam_role" "eb_role" { ... } resource "aws_iam_role_policy_attachment" "eb_role_policy" { ... } resource "aws_iam_instance_profile" "eb_instance_profile" { ... } resource "aws_elastic_beanstalk_application" "go_app" { ... } resource "aws_elastic_beanstalk_environment" "go_env" { ... } resource "aws_s3_bucket" "go_app_bucket" { ... } resource "random_string" "bucket_suffix" { ... } resource "aws_s3_bucket_object" "go_app_zip" { ... }</pre>
Uses a resource that is outdated or deprecated	<pre>#119 ... resource "aws_s3_bucket_server_side_encryption_configuration" "example" { bucket = aws_s3_bucket.mybucket.id rule { apply_server_side_encryption_by_default { kms_master_key_id = aws_kms_key.mykey.arn sse_algorithm = "aws:kms" } } }</pre>	<pre>#119 ... resource "aws_s3_bucket" "example" { bucket = "my-unique-bucket-name-12345" server_side_encryption_configuration { rule { apply_server_side_encryption_by_default { sse_algorithm = "aws:kms" kms_master_key_id = aws_kms_key.example.key_id } } } }</pre>

Table 12. Dimension 1: Intent Validation Error Examples - Misconfiguration Errors Sub-Category

Atomic Error	Dataset Infrastructure-as-Code	Generated Infrastructure-as-Code
Uses correct resources but misconfigured them	<pre>#27 # Elastic Beanstalk Environment for the web tier ... resource "aws_elastic_beanstalk_environment" "web_tier" { name = "my-web-tier-env" application = aws_elastic_beanstalk_application. my_application.name solution_stack_name = "64bit_Amazon_Linux_2023_v4.3.0_ running_Python_3.9" tier = "WebServer" setting { namespace = "aws:autoscaling:launchconfiguration" name = "IamInstanceProfile" value = aws_iam_instance_profile.eb_ec2_profile. name } }</pre>	<pre>#27 ... resource "aws_elastic_beanstalk_environment" " web_environment" { name = "my-web-env" application = aws_elastic_beanstalk_application. my_application.name solution_stack_name = "64bit_Amazon_Linux_2_v5.4.2_ running_PHP_7.4" setting { namespace = "aws:autoscaling:launchconfiguration" name = "IamInstanceProfile" value = aws_iam_instance_profile.eb_ec2_profile. name } }</pre>

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